

Single Particle Degeneracy in the Maxwell-Boltzmann/ Canonical Distribution Case

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac FD and Bose-Einstein BE distributions may be obtained by maximizing the \ln of energy level degeneracies subject to the constraint of $\sum_i e_i n_i = E_{ave}$ in the MB case (canonical distribution) and this constraint together with a second one $\sum_i n_i = N_{ave}$ (grand canonical case) as shown in (1) page 182. In particular, in the MB case, a single energy level e_i with n_i particles is said to have the degeneracy $(g_i)^{n_i} / n_i!$ (which overcounts). This maximization process leads to the weight $g_i \exp(-e_i/T)$. Setting $g_i=1$, however, leads to the same weight $\exp(-e_i/T)$ so the MB factor is not a result of a single particle level degeneracy i.e. the direction in which the momentum vector points. To shed physical light on this situation, one may consider two particle scattering in the MB, FD and BE cases. In all three cases, $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$ (with $e=pp/2m$), but only in the MB case does $n(e_1)n(e_2)=n(e_3)n(e_4)$. This suggests that the single energy level e_i degeneracy levels e_i actually play a physical role in two body scattering for the FD and BE cases, but not in the MB case. Thus, calculating probabilities based on counting still involves the physics related to the interactions in the problem. Degeneracies may exist and may or may not need to be part of the counting of arrangements.

As a specific example, we note that in (1) $(g_i)^{n_i} / n_i!$ is used to count degenerate arrangements for the MB case (on page 182). This same expression is used in (1) on page 194 to describe a method by Fowler and Darwin to obtain the MB single particle probability $\exp(-e_i/T)$. In that case, g_i is taken to be a parameter which is ultimately set to 1 and not the degeneracy of the single particle level. This begs the question: When should single energy e_i degeneracy be included in the counting of states?

Single Energy e_i Level Degeneracies and Probability Distributions

Statistical mechanics is often linked with calculating various equally weighted arrangements and then maximizing the \ln of this quantity subject to constraints. Given that single particle single energy levels have degeneracies, for example due to the direction in which the momentum vector points for the same e_i value, one might include these degeneracies in a calculation of arrangements which ultimately leads to the probability distribution. In particular, in (1), the following three arrangement calculations are given for $n(e_i)$ particles in the e_i level which has a degeneracy of g_i :

(1) Bose-Einstein Case

Arrangements due to single particle e_i degeneracy = $\text{Product over } i \text{ } (n_i+g_i-1)! / \{n_i! (g_i-1)!\}$
((1a))

(2) Fermi - Dirac Case

Arrangements due to single particle e_i degeneracy = $\text{Product over } i \text{ } g_i! / \{n_i! (g_i-n_i)!\}$ ((1b))

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case:

Arrangements due to single particle e_i degeneracy = $N! \prod_i g_i^{n_i} / n_i!$ ((1c))

In all three cases, the degeneracy g_i appears as a linear factor multiplied by a function of e_i and possibly the chemical potential u . In the FD and BE cases, the degeneracy g_i is critical to obtaining the distribution in e_i , u , while in the MB case it is not. For the MB case, one may maximize:

$\ln \{ N! / \prod_i n_i! \}$ subject to $\sum_i e_i n_i = E_{ave}$ ((2))

One need not consider single energy level e_i degeneracy at all to obtain $\exp(-e_i/T)$ even though this degeneracy exists and could certainly be included in an arrangement expression as done in ((1c)).

We thus ask: Are there physical considerations which dictate what type of arrangements should be considered?

Two Particle Scattering

One may imagine two particle elastic scattering occurring in MB, FD and BE gases. In all three cases:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((3))$$

Only in the MB case, however, does one have: $p(e_1) p(e_2) = p(e_3) p(e_4)$ ((4))

Equating ((4)) with ((3)) up to a multiplicative constant yields: $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((5)).

No considerations of degeneracy are included. Rather it is assumed that p =probability is only a function of e_i and that only e_i is relevant in the two body scattering which creates the physical equilibrium. Thus, even though a particular e_i may have many p_i (momentum) vectors which have the same energy, only one is needed for the reaction ((3)). Thus, degeneracy does not enter i.e.

$$p(e_1) g_1 p(e_2) g_2 \neq p(e_3) g_3 p(e_4) g_4 \quad ((5))$$

In the FD and BE cases, one does not have ((4)) so there is more information needed about the scattering. In particular, in the FD case, if a particle exists in a state e_i , another identical one may not scatter into that state. In the BE case there is an enhanced probability to scatter into a state with more particles than with fewer. Thus there are physical considerations which exist and are ultimately linked to the kind of arrangements one should calculate.

The Canonical Distribution

In (1) (page 195) a canonical type distribution approach (the Darwin-Fowler) is applied to calculating the single particle $\exp(-e_i/T)$ MB factor. It is assumed one has an ensemble of n_0 systems with energy E_0 , n_1 with E_1 etc such that:

$$\sum_i n_i = N \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i E_i n_i = MU \quad ((6b))$$

The goal is to maximize: $N! / \prod_i n_i!$ Subject to ((6a)) ((6b)) ((7))

One may see that ((7)) does not introduce any ideas of energy degeneracies g_i in E_i .

In performing the calculation, the form:

$$W(\{n_i\}) = N! \prod_i g_i^{n_i} / n_i! \quad ((8))$$

is used, but g_i are now not degeneracies as on page 182, but math factors which are ultimately set to 1. The calculation suggests considering all possible $\{n_i\}$ sets which satisfy ((6a)) and ((6b)).

$$F(N,U) = \sum_{\{n_i\} \text{ sets}} W(\{n_i\}) \quad ((9))$$

It then introduces a math function which resembles the canonical distribution:

$$G(N,z) = \sum_U (0 \text{ to infinite}) z^{NU} F(N,U) \quad ((10)) \quad z = \text{a complex number}$$

((10)) sums over all possible U values while ((6a)), ((6b)) deal with a specific U . The objective of ((10)) seems to be to obtain a single system partition function form:

$$f(z) = 1 + z^{E_1} + z^{E_2} \dots \quad ((11)) \quad \text{It is assumed that } N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$$

We leave the details to (1) pages 195-197, but the point we wish to make is that no system degeneracies associated with E_i are included. The final result is the MB result $\exp(-E_i/T)$.

The Canonical Distribution A Priori

In (1) (above section) the form ((10)) which has the appearance of a canonical distribution is introduced as essentially a math trick. We ask whether there might be a physical reason for creating a canonical distribution because one may maximize $\ln N! / \prod_i n_i!$ Subject to $\sum_i E_i n_i = MU$ without any consideration of a canonical distribution. The result, however, yields $\exp(-E_i/T)$ which in a normalized form is:

$$p(E_i) = \exp(-E_i/T) / \sum_i \exp(-E_i/T) \quad ((12))$$

Thus: Sum over $i \exp(-e_i/T)$ is a sum of possible single particle probabilities. If one considers N particles, one might create the following form which treats all particles equally i.e. might write a priori:

$$Z = \left\{ \sum_i p(e_i) \right\}^N \quad ((13))$$

Z always includes N particles, but the summands contain various different energies. It may be noted that when expanding this result, some terms are permutations of each other. The weight factor for permutations is:

$$N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \quad ((14))$$

This is exactly the factor to be maximized subject to the Sum over $i e_i n(e_i) = E$ constraint. The maximization yields the unnormalized factor $\exp(-e_i/T)$. The form Z is equivalent to:

$$Z = \sum_i \exp(-E_i/T) \text{ where } E_i = \sum_j e_j n_j \text{ such that } \sum_j n_j = N. \quad ((15))$$

Thus a canonical form, i.e. ((15)), using $p(e_i)$ from maximization yields the correct single particle normalization factor in ((12)).

We note that $\exp(-e_i/T)$ may be obtained without any considerations of single particle degeneracies. This seems to be physically correct in the temperature regions for which the MB distribution holds, but is not true in general as the FD and BE distributions show.

Grand Canonical Case

The grand canonical case which sums using $\exp(-(E-uN)/T)$ factors such that $E = \sum_i n(i)e_i$, displays the degeneracy issue as we have noted before. In particular, for a fixed e_i , one sums over n values from 0 to infinite (integers), but does not include any degeneracy factor which might be associated with having different n particles in a given e_i state.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that statistical mechanical probability distributions are often considered to follow from counting possible arrangements and maximizing subject to various constraints. It is possible, however, to have single energy level e_i degeneracies in a problem. Do these affect the number of arrangements? In the MB case, they may be ignored and the $\exp(-e/T)$ result obtained. In the FD and BE case, they are important and cannot be ignored. This seems to be directly linked to the physical elastic scattering problem: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. Only in the MB case does one have $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$. Thus counting/arrangements seem to be linked to physical properties in particular to ones linked with physical scattering which creates the equilibrium. As a result, one does not necessarily consider all degeneracies in a problem when counting. This is particularly evident when using the grand canonical distribution and summing

over the number of particles for a given ϵ_i i.e. $\exp(-(\epsilon_i - \mu) n(i)/T)$ where $n(i)$ ranges from 0 to infinite for the boson case. No degeneracies are included with the different $n(i)$ values.

References

1. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987)